

A Math Teacher's Plea

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I stand in the class, patient and steady,
Explaining numbers and formulas, always ready
But when I look in your eyes, I can hardly see.
The excitement for Math that I long for would be.

With each explanation, I try to find a way,
To make learning Math easier and brighten each day.
Still, many of you are afraid of numbers, and that is hard to break.
It stands in the way of learning, a challenge everyone should take.

I hope that one day you will all realize,
Math is not something to fear, but an aid in our lives.
In every computation, whether great or small,
There is meaning and purpose for it all.

Teaching is challenging, and patience is always tested.
Why can't others see that Math is something you'll always need?
We use math when we shop, make plans, or work for our future.
Math helps us achieve our dreams and enjoy life's grandeur.

My students, this is my plea: do not fear, accept the learning path,
I will walk beside you until you learn to love Math.
Cherish Mathematics, accept its noble role,
With effort and with fortitude, it will make you whole.

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